

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH

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Annotation: This research helps students to make reading more effective, influences the student's knowledge and inner world, and thus helps them understand how classroom activities and teachers' decisions create or limit children's learning opportunities. will give. The purpose of this article is to teach students English.

Keywords: method, methods, reader, teaching, learning, foreign language, competence, young learners, vocabulary, activity, comprehension.

While traditional methodologies such as voice and direct methods still offer useful elements, they are clearly outdated in the modern classroom. The communicative approach, which dates back to the late 1990s, is one of the most recent advances in modern language teaching. In this article, we will take a closer look at four new teaching strategies that will focus on students.

Task-based approach:

Creating traditional curricula and classroom planning revolved around topics that were beneficial to students. This means that students learn grammar and vocabulary that teachers need for students to know. This approach separates individual skills and competencies to teach students the materials they need to know how to respond to their goals and objectives. Exemplary tasks can be more advanced tasks, such as ordering at a restaurant, booking a hotel room, or criticizing a movie or expressing your opinion about a policy. In this approach, the language taught revolves around the task itself, not the other task. For this method to work, teachers need to understand their students and requirements in order to develop lessons that will help their students succeed. Grammar, vocabulary, and language skills are tools that allow students to achieve end results.

Class Discussion

Another way for students to teach each other is through class discussions. As students take turns discussing the subject, you can assess their knowledge and discover which students grasp the concepts and to what extent.

Lexical curriculum

This approach is based on the basic language that students need to know taking into account their needs. However, professional students need very specific dictionaries relevant to their field. For example, “benefit” is a very important term for business students, just as “scalpel” is for medical students.

In addition, any other language taught outside of this core language should be complementary and designed to enable students to communicate in their respective fields. Topics like movies and hobbies can take precedence over things like booking a hotel or describing a work experience. However, all areas have common skills such as saying your name or providing personal information.

Because this approach is content-oriented, assignments and homework assignments should focus on students’ real needs. Therefore, assessment should be based on what students have actually achieved. Examples of these assessments include writing an email or applying for an interview to apply for a job.

Providing Feedback

Students don’t always know if they’re doing a good job without you telling them so. Regularly provide written or verbal feedback for individual or group assignments and make this part of your classroom culture. Remember that students often don’t know why something is wrong, so whenever possible and time permitting, take a few moments to explain why you’ve marked something “incorrect” on tests and assignments. It’s also a great idea to conduct regular “group feedback” sessions based on patterns you’re seeing in your students’ work. If a fair share of your students seem to be struggling with a concept, it’s often more beneficial to create a lesson targeting that topic and discussing the patterns you’ve seen in class work generally. Remember, of course, to provide plenty of positive feedback as well as feedback indicating where a student has room to grow or what a student should do differently. Encouragement helps keep students’ morale, inspiration, and drive high. And finally, it can be beneficial to turn the tables sometimes. Let the students provide you feedback to tell you how you’re doing as well. You can do this in the form of a discussion, issue class surveys (that can be answered anonymously or not), or ask students to email you with feedback.

Lesson Objective Transparency

Rather than letting your students figure out what they should be learning on their own, just tell them. Clearly state your lesson goals or objectives. You could announce it in class or write it on the board. Just make it simple and clear for all

of your students to understand. Then, they know what they're working towards and what they should know by the end of the class. This also really helps to reduce student anxiety come test time.

Listening Comprehension Through this, students can improve their speaking skills. Hearing is a receptive form of speech activity. Comprehension of speech during listening is mainly based on auditory sensations. Perception of what we hear, repetition in the form of inner speech. It is not possible to listen without the speech engine checker running. Of course, inner speech requires the ability to speak this language. Comprehension of fallen speech is accompanied by intellectual activity, which, by the time of comprehension, involves the recognition of the means of speech and the interpretation of content. When classes are non-traditional, tasks are divided into pairs or small groups of students depending on their type, with students working in groups or individually. For example, at the beginning of a lesson, the teacher makes a plan with the students and shares the news. Each student will participate in this plan and share the news with each other. As a result, there is a mutual exchange of knowledge and all students become familiar with the topic. Some exercises are done by a couple or a group of students. To work in a group, students are given the following tasks: organizing discussions, discussing a topic with role-playing, working with high technology. To work in pairs, they include dialogues, grammar materials, and reading. Using these methods, we can force all students to attend the lesson and the teacher can help each student according to his or her requirements.

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